

The Role of Tourism Industry in Economy

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***Annotation.** Tourism is vital to the success of many economies worldwide and has been a widely researched area for many years. Tourism is vital for the success of many economies around the world. There are several benefits of tourism on host destinations. Tourism boosts the revenue of the economy, creates thousands of jobs, develops the infrastructures of a country, and plants a sense of cultural exchange between foreigners and citizens.*

***Keywords:** Tourism, Innovation, Travelling, Destinations, Economy.*

INTRODUCTION

So, what is the tourism industry? First, it is important to define what the ‘*tourism industry*’ means. Essentially, it refers to all activity related to the short-term movement of people to locations away from where they usually reside. It is one of the world’s largest industries, and the economies of many nations are driven, to a large extent, by their tourist trade.

It is also a wide-ranging industry, which includes the hotel industry, the transport industry, and several additional industries or sectors. It is vital to understand that the tourist industry is linked to movement to different locations, based on leisure, business, and some additional travel motivators.

With that being said, according to the most common definitions, the tourism industry does not cover activities related to travel where the person intends to stay in their destination for longer than one year. As an example, this means that expatriates and long-term international students are not technically classed as tourists. Governments that rely on tourism for a big percentage of their revenue invest a lot in the infrastructure of the country. They want more and more tourists to visit their country which means that safe and advanced facilities are necessary. This leads to new roads and highways, developed parks, improved public spaces, new airports, and possibly better schools and hospitals. Safe and innovative infrastructures allow for a smooth flow of goods and services. Moreover, local people experience an opportunity for economic and educational growth. Tourism creates a cultural exchange between tourists and local citizens. Exhibitions, conferences, and events usually attract foreigners. Organizing authorities usually gain profits from registration fees, gift sales, exhibition spaces, and sales of media copyright. Furthermore, foreign tourists bring diversity and cultural enrichment to the hosting country.

Tourism is a great opportunity for foreigners to learn about a new culture, but it also creates many opportunities for local citizens. It allows young entrepreneurs to establish new products and services that would not be sustainable on the local population of residents alone. Moreover, residents experience the benefits that come with tourism occurring in their own country. Tourism is critical in creating goodwill among people and, as a result, socioeconomic growth in the country. Tourism as an industry contributes significantly to the country's foreign exchange reserves and provides direct and indirect job possibilities to a broad segment of the population. Furthermore, supporting a nation's handicrafts and fine arts aids in the preservation of nature's beauty, cultural legacy of the country, and soil tradition, as well as strengthening the process of national integration and global brotherhood. For analytical purposes, it is important to distinguish between different forms of tourism. For example, tourism is often divided into two main categories: international tourism and domestic tourism, which is determined by the tourist's permanent residence's territorial limit. There is no minimum duration of travel required to qualify as a tour, and the important component is the movement away from the permanent residence to the destination or locations that are not in the same region. This article discusses the importance of tourism and the hospitality industry in economic growth.

Elite tourism and mass tourism are two more types of tourism that we encounter. An elite tourist travels with a self-contained mentality and is always self-contained. He might be an antiquarian, a naturalist, or an adventurer visiting locations that few people visit or are unfamiliar with. Because he is a snob by nature and a nonconformist, if not eccentric, his pleasure of the location is lessened as visitor traffic increases. For that reason alone, he prefers less accessible locations. The nature-loving visitor would frequently go around a mountain or a game sanctuary by himself. The relationship between nature and himself is the fundamental desire of such a nature-loving traveler. He wants to share his experience with his friends, relatives, and other group travellers. When visiting a historical place or a monument, the antique lover likes isolation. The difficulties in traveling to a tourist attraction may serve as a challenge for him if he is motivated by the spirit of adventure. He adapts well to local conditions and is unconcerned about accommodations, food, and other amenities.

Tourism as an industry is a major contributor to foreign exchange reserves in the country, providing a large proportion of the population with direct and indirect work opportunities. In addition, it will promote the arts and crafts of a nation to preserve the beauty of nature, its cultural heritage and the history of land and to advance the process of national unity and global brotherhood. It is necessary to distinguish between various kinds of tourism for analytical reasons.

Tourism offers a wide range of benefits, including economic benefits for countries attracting many visitors, due to the money they spend not only on their actual stay, but also on local businesses. It also provides many jobs for people working in the transport and hospitality industry, among others. Moreover, tourism can potentially improve relationships between nation-states or businesses, create opportunities for entertainment and recreation, and improve the value of a currency. It can also open up cultural exchange opportunities, while for tourists, it can lead to improved happiness, well-being, and education.

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